

Glycerol-Enhanced Gum Karaya Hydrogel Films with Sandwich-like Structure enriched with Octenidine for Antibacterial Action Against Multidrug-resistant Bacteria

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ABSTRACT: This study explores the innovative approach in the development of freeze-dried hydrogel films, leveraging the unique properties of gum Karaya (GK), poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA), poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG), and glycerol, with a coating of octenidine dihydrochloride (OCT). These innovative hydrogel films exhibit at certain concentration a sandwich-like structure, achieved through tailored freeze-drying process, which enhances transparency, and mechanical stability. OCT incorporation provides a superior antibacterial performance, effectively combating multidrug-resistant bacteria with a controlled and gradual release mechanism, surpassing conventional OCT solutions that require frequent reapplication for infected wound treatment without creation of bacterial resistance. Advanced environmental scanning electron microscopy (A-ESEM) reveals complex microstructure of the hydrogel, highlighting the dense surface layer and interconnected porous bulk. Variations in glycerol concentrations proved to significantly impact hydrogels properties, increasing glycerol concentration decrease pore size (around 4.5 μm) while enhancing polymer network density and flexibility. While low concentration increases pore size (7.8 to 15.6 μm), impacting increased swelling behavior and hydrolytic stability. OCT's rapid antibacterial action, releasing over 30% within the first hour and maintaining prolonged activity for up to two weeks, emphasis the materials potential for diverse applications. Hydrogels remarkable transparency,

antibacterial efficacy against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial, and structural stability suggest promising uses in transparent dressings, biomedical devices, and infection-resistant surfaces.

KEYWORDS: Hydrogels, biopolymers, gum Karaya, poly(vinyl alcohol), glycerol, octenidine dihydrochloride, antibacterial, A-ESEM

1. Introduction

Hydrogels, as versatile and highly tunable materials, have garnered significant attention due to their unique composition-structure-property relationships, which enable their use in advanced applications ranging from biomedical devices to antibacterial coatings^{1,2}. Firstly synthesized by Wichterle and Lim, hydrogels have evolved significantly over the past half-century, becoming essential in various fields due to their tunable structural, mechanical and biological properties^{3,4}. Characterized by their three-dimensional structures, hydrogels consist of a cross-linked polymer network that is hydrophilic and insoluble in water, allowing them to bind and retain significant water, mimicking natural extracellular matrix (ECM)^{5,6}. Their adaptability and a wide range of fabrication methods allow for fine-tuning their composition, making them suitable for diverse applications, including biomedical devices, coatings, antibacterial surfaces, wound healing, and flexible electronics^{3,7}.

Despite extensive research on hydrogels, transparent hydrogels composed of naturally antimicrobial biopolymers like gum Karaya with synthetic polymers such as PVA, in combination with plasticizers poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) and glycerol fabricated using freeze-drying represents a novel approach that uniquely balances biocompatibility, mechanical stability, and bioactivity. This study explores this innovative combination to overcome limitations in existing hydrogel formulations. Hydrogel composition, fabrication method and cross-linking mechanism significantly impact the final properties of the hydrogel, such as mechanical stability, swelling or transparency. Freeze-drying is a fabrication method widely used in the food and pharmaceutical industry to stabilize products, and it can be utilized in hydrogel fabrication. Unlike traditional film casting or freeze-thaw methods, freeze drying in the first step freezes water, preventing chemical biochemical or microbiological processes, then removes water from the hydrogel matrix by sublimating ice, forming a controlled microstructure with interconnected pores^{8,9}. This property is exploited in hydrogel fabrication as it produces material with uniform pores of size depending on hydrogel composition, enhanced swelling capacity, increased surface area, mechanical properties, and the ability to

easily incorporate bioactive molecules^{10,11}. The addition of plasticizers such as glycerol or PEG increases hydrogel elasticity and transparency, which is essential for transparent coatings applications in tissue engineering^{12,13}.

Gum Karaya (GK) is an industrially important polysaccharide, highly biocompatible and biodegradable as a natural compound with inherited antimicrobial activity^{14,15,16}. It is an abundant and relatively inexpensive material derived as a resin from the *Sterculia urens* tree that can form gels and potentially profitable commercial products in combination with other polymers (PVA, chitosan¹⁷, silk fibroin¹⁸). Synthetic polymers, namely PVA, PEG, poloxamers, and poly(N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone) (PVP), poly(acrylic acid) (pAA), are used as wound dressings, as they possess high water absorption and retention, gel formation, and sufficient mechanical strength¹⁹.

PVA, a highly hydrophilic synthetic biopolymer soluble in water, possesses biocompatibility, biodegradability and non-toxicity while having excellent film-forming properties due to the hydrogen bonding of -OH groups and creation of crystalline domains resulting in mechanically strong, cross-linked PVA hydrogels²⁰⁻²¹. Unfortunately, inadequate elasticity, brittleness, and stiffness are incompatible with its use alone as a hydrogel dressing^{22,23}. PVA brittleness can be reduced using plasticizers. Glycerol is a transparent, non-toxic, and viscous liquid widely used in the biomedical field as a plasticizer and cryoprotectant^{24,25}. These properties can be utilized in hydrogel fabrication using the freeze-thaw or freeze-drying methods. Glycerol molecules in a hydrogel matrix influence its microstructure and reduce the creation of crystallinities that affect hydrogel properties, such as increased transparency and elasticity^{20,24,26}. PEG is a hydrophilic polymer widely used in hydrogel fabrication for its ability to form a highly swellable network with chain flexibility and thermal resistance²⁷. It is suitable for use in the biomedical industry for its non-toxic and inert behaviour²⁸.

Hydrogel bioactivity, namely antibacterial properties, can be secured in different ways; a hydrogel matrix composed of various chemicals has antibacterial activity on its own, or the hydrogel serves as a drug delivery system by adding antibiotics, antiseptics, antibacterial proteins/peptides or nanoparticles²⁹⁻³⁰. These bioactive modifications are essential nowadays due to increased multidrug resistance against conventional antibiotics since they represent a global problem and threaten the healthcare system, influencing millions of lives^{31,32}. This work secures antibacterial activity by integrating antiseptic octenidine dihydrochloride (OCT), enhancing antimicrobial performance to treat potential or present infection. OCT has a wide antimicrobial spectrum and is highly effective at lower concentrations (0.1%) in a short time

while covering many bacterial or fungal strains (including multidrug-resistant strains), e.g. methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains without the development of antimicrobial resistance. Its cationic charge allows interaction with a negatively charged microbial cell wall that inhibits cell functions³³. OCT is primarily used in solutions or carbomer-based gels, which must be frequently reapplied, so there is room for developing a more advanced system for OCT drug delivery. Current hydrogel formulations with OCT (e.g. Octenisept) do not possess other requirements, such as adequate mechanical stability, OCT sustainable release, and biodegradability.

The present study provides insight into the synergic effect of OCT antiseptics, antibacterial natural polysaccharide and hydrophilic synthetic polymers combined with advanced fabrication techniques, resulting in a sandwich-like transparent film. The integration of OCT into the hydrogel matrix exhibited sustained release and antibacterial action and addresses the growing challenge of antibiotic resistance by offering a broad-spectrum antimicrobial strategy³⁴. This novel hydrogel film formulation enhances its functionality, making it suitable for applications beyond wound care, such as in antibacterial coatings and infection-resistant materials.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Gum Karaya (GK, Merck, Germany), sodium hydroxide (Lar-Nech, Czech Republic), hydrochloric acid (Lar-Nech, Czech republic), ethanol 96% (Lar-Nech, Czech republic), poly(vinyl alcohol) ($M_w = 130\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$, 99+% hydrolysed) (Merck, USA), poly(ethylene glycol) 400 (Merck, Czech republic), glycerol anhydrous (Penta s.r.o., Czech republic), Milli-Q ultrapure water Type I according to ISO 3696, normal saline (0.9% NaCl) (Braun, Germany), octenidine dihydrochloride, 98% (Alfa Aesar, China), Mueller Hinton Broth (Merck, UK), DMEM (Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium), FBS (fetal bovine serum), penicillin/streptomycin, trypsin/EDTA, XTT ((2,3-bis-(2-methoxy-4-nitro-5-sulfophenyl)-2H-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide), and PBS were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Modification and Purification of Natural Gum Karaya

Prior to use, the GK powder was deacetylated to increase its solubility in water following the deacetylation method described in Postulkova et al.¹⁴ The original GK powder was mixed with ultrapure water (obtaining 2 wt% solution), placed on a magnetic stirrer at 300 rpm, and

homogenized for 24 hours at room temperature. Deacetylation of the solubilized original GK powder was provided by the addition of $1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) in a ratio of three parts of the GK dispersion and one part of NaOH and stirred for 10 minutes at room temperature. The addition of NaOH caused an increase in the pH value to 12; to adjust pH to neutral (7), a diluted solution of $0.3 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ hydrochloric acid was used. The increase in solubility was carried out by deacetylation of the original GK, where hydroxyl groups replaced acetyl groups. The modified GK was centrifuged at $25 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 3234 rcf to remove impurities. The remaining impurities were eliminated by filtration through polypropylene filters for better purification. Finally, the GK was then precipitated in ethanol in a 2:1 ratio and freeze-dried (freeze dryer Epsilon 2-10D LSCplus, Martin Christ, Germany). The powder was frozen at $-30 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then freeze-dried at $-35 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a pressure of 1 mBar for 15 hours. Then, secondary drying occurred at $25 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under a pressure of 0.01 mBar until decreasing Δp (the pressure change was up to 10%). The dry sample of GK was then crushed into powder and stored in a desiccator at room temperature.

2.2.2. Hydrogel Films Fabrication by Freeze-drying Method

The modified GK powder was dissolved in ultrapure water, obtaining 2 wt% solutions after solubilisation for 3 hours under reflux at $90 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to prevent evaporation of the vapour. A 4 wt% PVA solution was dissolved in ultrapure water under reflux for 2 hours at $100 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Hydrogel solutions were prepared using different PVA and GK ratios (Table 1). The prepared solutions were homogenised with a magnetic stirring at 300 rpm at room temperature overnight with the addition of PEG and glycerol. The ratios of solutions used for hydrogel films are summarised in Table 1. Based on glycerol concentrations, two distinct sample series were named: Series 1 (25 wt%) and Series 2 (75 wt%). The final polymer mixture was centrifuged at 3234 rcf to remove excess bubbles and impurities in the solution, then poured into Petri dishes and dried by freeze-drying method, same as used for GK powder. The final dry hydrogel films were stored in a desiccator at room temperature.

1.1.1. Hydrogel Film Coating by Antimicrobial OCT

The OCT stock solutions were prepared by dissolution of OCT in ethanol (96%) at given concentrations (375 and $750 \text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and stirred until homogenised. Two materials (1GPgH, 2GPgH) were used for the coating with an OCT concentration of 0.05 and $0.1 \text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, as shown in Table 1, according to the preferable concentrations for treating chronic wounds and multidrug-resistant organisms³⁵. The hydrogel films were coated by applying a defined amount

of OCT solution onto the hydrogel surface. Subsequently, the coated hydrogel films were dried at room temperature, followed by the evaporation of the remaining ethanol at 60 °C, preventing the hydrogel film degradation. The coated hydrogel film was sealed in plastic plates and stored at room temperature.

Table 1: Summary of the sample composition: the first number (1, 2 or 3) in marking samples represents the different ratio between GK:PVA, G means GK, P states for PVA, gL means 25 wt% of glycerol, gH is for 75 wt% of glycerol, oL means OCT of 0.05 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and oH with OCT of 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ concentration.

Sample name	(GK:PVA) ratio		Glycerol amount (wt%)	OCT concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)
1GPgL	1	1	25	-
1GPgH	1	1	75	-
2GPgL	1	2	25	-
2GPgH	1	2	75	-
3GPgL	1.5	1	25	-
3GPgH	1.5	1	75	-
1GPgH-oL	1	1	75	0.05
1GPgH-oH	1	1	75	0.1
2GPgH-oL	1	2	75	0.05
2GPgH-oH	1	2	75	0.1

1.1.2. Optical Properties

The colour values of the hydrogel films with different GK content were determined using the CIELAB colour system on the UV-VIS Spectrophotometer V-730, JACSO (USA). The CIELAB system expresses colour and lightness as three parameters: L^* , a^* , and b^* . L^* characterises lightness, describing the relative intensity of light with values from 0 in absolute black to 100 in absolute white, and can be used to determine the material transparency. The other two parameters describe a colour coordinate: a^* from green (-) to red (+) and b^* from

blue (-) to yellow (+). The difference between the samples in the dry and hydrated state can be objectively evaluated using the colour difference E in the following equation.

$$E = \sqrt{L^2 + a^2 + b^2} \quad (1)$$

The L , a , and b represent the colour parameter values of the colour parameters of dry or hydrated hydrogel film samples at the water equilibrium to compare the lightness and the colour difference E in the wavelength region of 800 – 380 nm in a quartz cuvette with the background of the empty cuvette.

The opacity of the hydrogel film was determined using a UV-VIS spectrometer, measuring the light absorbance of dry/hydrated hydrogel films at 600 nm (A_{600}) against the air in an empty cuvette. Hydrogel film opacity was obtained using equation³⁶ (2):

$$Opacity = \frac{A_{600}}{d} \quad (2)$$

Here, d states the thickness of the sample in the dry and hydrated states. Graphs and statistics were created in OriginPro2020b. Each measurement was repeated five times to obtain a reliable standard deviation.

1.1.3. Swelling Behaviour

The gravimetric method was used to determine the swelling behaviour of freeze-dried hydrogel films and coated hydrogel films. Testing was carried out in normal saline (0.9% NaCl) at a temperature of 37 °C. All samples were cut into circular shapes with approximately the same weight. The samples were placed in a Petri dish and weighed in the dry state before testing. The measurement then occurred at the following intervals: 1, 5, 10, 20, 40, 60, 90, and 120 min. All samples were placed in the incubator to keep the temperature at 37 °C. Before each weighting, the surface water on the sample was removed by filtration paper, and after that, the sample was weighted on analytical balances. The swelling behaviour was determined by the swelling ratio using Equation 3:

$$Swelling\ ratio\ [-] = \frac{w_s - w_d}{w_d} \quad (3)$$

The dry sample and that of w_d represent the weight of w_s , which represents the swollen state of the hydrogel film sample in the equation. Each measurement was repeated five times to obtain a reliable standard deviation.

1.1.4. Hydrogel film Weight Loss

Hydrogel film degradation was evaluated with samples immersed in Mili-Q type I ultrapure water and incubated at 37 °C. First, the material was weighed to obtain w_{max} (weight of the swelled material in time intervals correlated with the maximum weight of the swelled sample, specific for each sample). Subsequently, weight was measured in time intervals of 1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days, obtaining w_s . Hydrogel film degradation was evaluated using the following equation (4).

$$\text{Weight loss [\%]} = 100 - \frac{w_s \times 100}{w_{max}} \quad (4)$$

Each measurement was repeated four times.

1.1.5. ATR- FTIR analysis

The presence of the functional groups on the surface and bulk of the samples was confirmed by Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy with attenuated total reflectance (ATR-FTIR) with an ATR-FTIR spectroscope Vertex 70/70v (Bruker, USA). Samples were measured in the form of hydrogel films, raw material (GK, PVA) in powder form, and coated hydrogel films. The infrared spectrum was scanned between 3700 – 700 cm^{-1} with the number of scans equal to 32 and a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} .

1.1.6. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

The hydrogel film and OCT-coated films' thermal stability was characterised by thermogravimetric analysis performed using Discovery TGA, TA Instruments, Nicolet iS10 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The heating rate was set at 10 °C/min in the nitrogen atmosphere on platinum plates ranging from 40 to 700 °C.

1.1.7. Tensile Strength Test

The tensile strength and elongation of the swollen hydrogel films were determined using the RSA-G2 TA rheometer. The dried hydrogel films were cut into strips (3×0.5 cm), placed between the grips, and swelled in water at 37 °C until they reached the maximum swelling ratio. Then, the measurement was performed at the constant linear rate set at 0.2 mm/s until the sample reached the breaking point.

1.1.8. Hydrogel Film Morphology

The surface microstructure of noncoated hydrogel film samples was studied using advanced environmental scanning electron microscopy (A-ESEM)^{37,38}. In-house modified A-ESEM QUANTA 650 FEG (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used under operating conditions: a beam accelerating voltage of 5 kV, beam current 53 pA, working distance 8.5 mm, and 200 Pa of water vapour pressure, using an Ionisation Secondary Electron Detector with an electrostatic Separator (ISEDS)^{39,40}. The thickness measurement of an antiseptic layer was carried out on freeze-fractured samples. The hydrogel film pieces were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen, fractured at $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and then fixed on the tilted stub. For detailed observation of hydrogel film pores, samples were in situ freeze-dried using the A-ESEM. Small hydrogel film samples ($2\times 2\text{ mm}$) were placed on a cooled specimen holder (Peltier stage) and cooled to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (cooling rate of $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$). When a temperature of $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was reached, the pumping process of the A-ESEM specimen chamber started, according to the low-temperature method for ESEM (LTM) described by Neděla et al.⁴¹ and used for the study of various samples^{42,43}. The samples were observed under the following operating conditions: specimen holder temperature of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ water vapour pressure of 150 Pa. The pore size of the prepared hydrogel films was characterised by A-ESEM visualisation using the image analyses programme SEM Image Pore Extractor (SEMIPE)⁴⁴, an automatic tool for pore-dimensional extraction from SEM images of freeze-dried hydrogel films.

1.1.9. EDS Elemental Analysis

Semiquantitative energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis (EDS) was performed to detect the presence of an antiseptic OCT. Analysis was carried out on freeze-dried samples (freeze-dryer Epsilon 2-10D LSCplus, Martin Christ, Germany). Chemical treatment-free and conductive coating-free samples were analysed using a Bruker Quantax 400 XFlash 6/60 EDS silicon drift detector under beam energy of 5 keV, beam current of 100 pA, working distance of 10 mm and water vapour pressure of 200 Pa. The EDS spectra were obtained from five regions of each sample.

1.1.10. OCT Quantification and Release

OCT was quantified using the UV-VIS V-730 Spectrophotometer, JACSO (USA) at 280 nm. The stock solution contained 1% OCT; the final concentrations for the calibration curve were in the range of 0.01 to $1.5\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of OCT in ethanol.

The release of OCT coated at various concentrations on the hydrogel film surface of two sample types (1GPgH and 2GPgH) was studied at 37 °C in a shaking incubator immersed in 1 mL of ultrapure water. At given time intervals (30 min, 1, 2, 4, 6, 10 hours and 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 12, and 14 days), all the solutions with released OCT were removed for quantification analysis using UV-VIS spectroscopy from the OCT calibration curve described above. The removed water was replaced with the same amount of ultrapure water preheated at 37 °C. The graphs were created in OriginPro 2020b. Each measurement was repeated three times.

Release data were applied to various mathematical drug release models to investigate the drug release kinetics of OCT. Two mathematical models were used in this study to obtain the R² value:

- a) Higuchi model which can be represented using the following equation (5):

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = K_h t^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

Where M_t/M_∞ represent the fraction of released drug in each time interval (t), M_t represents the amount of the drug in time, M_∞ is the amount of drug released after time ∞ , and K_h is represented as the Higuchi release kinetic constant.

- b) Korsmeyer-Peppas (KP) model, which can be interpreted as the following equation (6):

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = K_{kp} t^n \quad (6)$$

Where M_t/M_∞ represent the fraction of released drug in each time interval (t), M_t represents the amount of the drug in time, M_∞ is the amount of drug released after time ∞ , n is a drug release exponent, and K_{kp} is Korsmeyer release rate constant.

1.1.11. Cell Culture and Cytotoxicity Assay

NIH-3T3 fibroblast cells (Sigma-Aldrich) were cultured in DMEM medium supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin/streptomycin at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Cells were harvested by trypsinization in a 0.25% trypsin/EDTA solution in PBS at 80% confluence. The extract test was used to evaluate the cytotoxic effect of any leachable components or by-products of the hydrogel film. Each film was incubated with a complete DMEM culture medium at room temperature at 0.033 g·mL⁻¹ for 24 h. NIH-3T3 cells were seeded at a density of 10⁴ cells/well in a 96-well plate prior to starting the assay. After 24 hours of cell growth, the cell culture medium was removed and replaced with the extract medium. The cells were then incubated at

37°C and 5% CO₂ for 24 h. The XTT assay was used according to the manufacturer's protocols. The extract medium was removed from the well plate, and the cells were gently washed using a PBS buffer solution. 100 µL of fresh DMEM medium and 50 µL XTT (XTT, 1 mg·mL⁻¹ in PBS, pH 7.4) labelling mixture was then added per well. The absorbance was measured after 4 hours of incubation at 37°C with a plate reader at 450 nm.

1.1.12. Antibacterial Activity

Bacterial strains *Staphylococcus aureus* CCM 3953 (=ATCC 25923) and *Escherichia coli* CCM 3954 (=ATCC 25922) obtained from the Czech Collection of Microorganisms were utilized. Both bacterial strains serve as standard international reference strains for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Susceptibility testing was performed according to the standard broth microdilution methodology outlined by EUCAST with some modifications⁴⁵. The tested materials were placed in triplicate in a 24-well microplate (JET BIOFIL 24 Well, Guangzhou, China). Both bacterial strains were grown overnight in 10 ml of Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB; Oxoid, Merck, UK) at 37 °C. The overnight cultures were then centrifuged and resuspended in fresh MHB twice. The bacterial cultures were then diluted with fresh MHB to obtain a bacterial suspension with a final concentration of 5×10^5 CFU/mL). 1 mL of the suspension was added to the tested materials and sealed with sterile ThermalSeal[®] films (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). The microplates were incubated at 37 °C with shaking in a Tecan Infinite M200 PRO microplate reader (Tecan Trading AG, Trasadingen, Switzerland), and the optical density (A = 600 nm) of the bacterial suspension was measured every 5 min for 24 h to obtain bacterial growth curves.

1.1.13. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the OriginPro2020b and Statistica 64 programs. For each parameter, the data were expressed as mean values ± standard error of the mean of at least three samples (porosity, swelling, degradation, mechanical, antibacterial and cytotoxic tests). ANOVA and partial correlation analysis, Tukey's test, and the t-test for dependent samples were performed using a 95% significance level to evaluate the significance level of the different sample types for various analyses, including porosity, mechanical tests, and antibacterial tests; *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001, were considered to indicate statistically significant results.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Optical Properties of Freeze-dried Hydrogel Films

Colour evaluation and opacity tests were performed on dry and hydrated film samples to determine whether the hydrogel films could provide direct, transparent monitoring. **Table 2** shows that L^* , a^* , and b^* represent the hydrogel films' lightness, redness, and yellowness, depending on the hydrogel film composition or the state (dry/wet).

Table 2: The CIELAB colour space determines the colour of the hydrogel films (L^* , lightness, a^* - red, and b^* - yellow opponent values), total colour difference E^* , and materials' opacity.

Sample	Hydrogel film state	L^*	a^*	b^*	E^*	Opacity
1GPgL	Dry	0.5	0.1	0.8	0.9	4.3
	Hydrated	58.6	1.2	1.8	58.6	0.7
2GPgL	Dry	0.8	0.0	0.9	1.2	2.5
	Hydrated	22.4	1.3	4.6	22.9	2.7
3GPgL	Dry	1.4	0.1	1.1	1.8	4.8
	Hydrated	43.7	3.5	19.1	47.8	2.1
1GPgH	Dry	76.6	1.0	10.9	77.4	1.0
	Hydrated	40.5	2.7	11.0	42.1	2.0
2GPgH	Dry	67.2	1.6	13.2	69.0	1.6
	Hydrated	42.8	2.1	7.0	43.4	1.2
3GPgH	Dry	71.4	0.2	8.2	71.9	1.5
	Hydrated	42.2	3.7	19.7	46.7	1.5

The results show that the hydrogel films' redness (a^*) and yellowness (b^*) are not significantly different in most films within the same Series and state. However, the CIELAB values differ within the different dry and hydrated states and in Series with p -values > 0.05 . The composition strongly influences the lightness of the film, and the samples differ significantly ($p > 0.05$). The total colour difference increases significantly in all samples after water absorption, causing a

considerable change in the visual aspect, as seen in **Figure 1**. The Series 1 sample (25 wt% of glycerol) has a whitish colour in the dry state due to the presence of a highly porous network that becomes partially transparent in the hydrated state, followed by a slight increase in $+b^*$, indicating a yellowish colour. The increase in transparency in hydrated samples correlates with a decrease in opacity and a significant increase in hydrogel film lightness (L^*), accounting for ~ 117 times higher L^* when hydrated compared to dry state, and E^* is ~ 65 times higher. Sample 2GPgL has comparable E^* and L^* , accounting for ~ 18 times higher hydrated state values than in the dry state, which is influenced by a higher PVA concentration that creates a denser polymer network between PVA chains and glycerol. The hydrated state of hydrogel films is highly impacted by swelling behaviour, which leads to the expansion of the hydrogel film network and pore enlargement and completely changes the visual aspect of hydrogel film with a low glycerol content (25%). Porous freeze-dried hydrogel films in a hydrated state are generally transparent and rigid materials, as previously described in Sedlář et al.⁴⁶. In contrast, samples of Series with gH (75 wt% of glycerol) have high L^* (<67) and E^* (<70) values in the dry state, indicating hydrogel's transparency, which is visualized in **Figure 1** and can be attributed to the presence of optically transparent micropores and smooth hydrogel surface in the dry state. A high E^* value in Series 2 is highly influenced by the high value of L^* and a higher yellowish b^* (<8) value.

Hydrated samples slightly decrease L^* , indicating a decrease in transparency, which cannot be compared with Series 1. However, the samples are transparent enough to visualise the surface under the hydrogel (**Figure 1**), and a decrease in E^* is comparable with L^* , accounting for 1.5 – 1.8 times lower values when hydrated. A slight increase in opacity when samples are hydrated can be attributed to the enlargement of the porous network beneath the hydrogel surface with entrapped water within the matrix and glycerol.

Figure 1: The visual aspect of the hydrogel films 1GPgL, 2GPgL, 3GPgL, 1GPgH, 2GPgH, and 3GPgH in the dry and hydrated state.

3.2. Swelling Behaviour of Freeze-dried Films

The ability to swell and retain water is one of the essential properties of hydrogel films in creating a moist environment. Swelling curves are summarised in **Figure 2A**, and hydrogels with coated OCT are shown in **Figure 2B**. All hydrogel films tended to swell in normal saline with the ability to preserve saline within the structure, providing additional stability during the experiment (120 min). A higher swelling rate was observed for samples 1GPgL, 2GPgL (25 wt% of glycerol), and 3GPgH (75 wt% of glycerol), which decreased over time due to the fragile network caused by an insufficient or excessive concentration in the polymer network. According to the results, the highest water absorption was observed in sample 3GPgL,

accounting for SW = 5.5 with increasing tendency due to a high concentration of swellable GK that preferentially interacted with the liquid environment rather than remaining stable within the cross-linked network¹⁴. The least stable and swellable hydrogel was sample 3GPgH, with a higher concentration of glycerol and swellable GK and a tendency to swell and rapidly dissolve in the hydrated environment over time. An excess of glycerol (75%) in the polymer network caused hydrogel instability. The sample rapidly degraded during measurement due to the low concentration of gel-forming PVA and the higher concentration of swellable GK, which do not form a strong polymer network with glycerol plasticiser, and polymer chain entanglement (PVA, GK) is insufficient to maintain stability.

Figure 2: Swelling ratio of prepared hydrogel dressings depending on time (A) and of OCT-coated hydrogels (B)

In comparison, samples 3GPgL, 1GPgH, and 2GPgH create a stable polymer network over time due to higher polymer chain entanglement and cross-linking density through hydrogen bond interactions between PVA, glycerol, and water that remains stable throughout the experiment. A dense layer on the hydrogel surface in films 1GPgH or 2GPgH influences the swelling behaviour, as no visible pores enable quick swelling, resulting in a lower swelling behaviour followed by the preservation of the liquid within the hydrogel matrix in bulk. A decrease in swelling can also be attributed to the increased moisture content due to glycerol, which provides flexibility while limiting absorption⁴⁷. The addition of OCT did not significantly impact the SW despite the OCT coating being performed in ethanol, which precipitates GK. This process partially altered the hydrogel surface during the coating process. Sample 2GPgH-oH had a slightly lower swelling capacity than 2GPgH; in contrast, sample 1GPgH-oH in **Figure 2B**

showed a much lower swelling than 1GPgH. The altered surface caused a slight reduction in swelling capacity and decreased sample stability, affecting OCT release.

3.3. Hydrogel Film Hydrolytic Stability

The hydrolytic stability of the hydrogel films evaluated as a mass loss within a time interval was provided in ultrapure water in an incubator at 37 ° C for 28 days. Weight loss over time, shown in **Figure 3**, indicates that the stability of the hydrogel strongly depends on the ability to form a stable hydrogel network between the components. Sample 3GPgH was not included in the experiment due to its instability and rapid disintegration. A higher density of hydrogen bonds between PVA chains and glycerol creates a stable cross-linked network along with a chain entanglement of PVA and GK and crystalline domains of PVA (2GPgL, 1GPgH, 2GPgH). The smooth, non-porous surface in samples 1GPgH and 2GPgH (75 wt% of glycerol) can influence stability as it entraps and preserves fluid within the porous network in bulk. On the contrary, the 2GPgL sample has a high PVA concentration, which enables the formation of a strong polymer network (hydrogen bonding, chain entanglement, and crystalline domains), which enhances stability in the hydrated state for a long time⁶. Samples 1GPgL and 3GPgL (25 wt% of glycerol) exhibit a higher weight loss, possibly due to a higher non-crosslinked GK content that supports enormous water sorption within the matrix, as previously described by Drapalova et al.⁴⁸. After rapid swelling, the matrix weakens, and GK is washed from the hydrogel network, causing a decrease in weight.

Figure 3: Hydrogel film weight loss for a 28-day experiment in type I ultrapure water at 37 °C placed in an incubator.

3.4. Chemical Compositions Determined by ATR-FTIR

ATR Fourier-transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy was used to characterise specific chemical groups present in the hydrogel films and to study the effect of composition to confirm the presence or absence of these groups in the chemicals and prepared hydrogel films. Spectra of raw gum Karaya and PVA were already published¹⁸; prepared freeze-dried hydrogel film spectra are shown in **Figure 4A**. Since hydrogel films are formed by freeze-drying, the hydroxyl groups present in PVA, glycerol, and GK are capable of bonding via hydrogen bonds and are expected to create specific interactions that influence the final spectra of the hydrogel. All samples show a wide absorption band at 3660 to 3080 cm^{-1} , representing the hydroxyl stretching of GK, PVA, and glycerol with varying intensity, which is directly proportional to the number of present hydroxyl groups in the samples, as shown in **Figure 4A**. These samples tend to have a higher absorption band of the hydroxyl groups, indicating that not all hydroxyl groups are cross-linked via hydrogen bonding. On the contrary, hydrogel

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of the prepared hydrogel dressing with different ratios between components (A), spectra of 1GPgH hydrogel, OCT, and coated hydrogels 1GPgH-oL and 1GPgH-oH (B)

films 1GPgL, 2GPgL, and 3GPgL (25 wt% glycerol) have a lower intensity of -OH stretching (**Figure 4A**), corresponding to a lower presence of free hydroxyl groups and a higher formation of hydrogen bonding between components^{17,49}. The aliphatic C-H bonds of PVA are indicated by the band at 2940 cm^{-1} . In particular, the vibrations at 1605 and 1418 cm^{-1} belong to the vibrations of the carboxylate group due to the carboxylation of the uronic acid residues of GK. The vibration at 1420 cm^{-1} represents the -OH alcohol groups of PVA. The broad absorption

band at 1150 - 980 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of the characteristic C-O bond for the pyranose ring belonging to GK and the C-O bonds in PVA, PEG, and glycerol. Error! Reference source not found. **4B** compares the FTIR spectrum of raw OCT and OCT-coated hydrogel films. The spectrum of raw octenidine shows an absorption band at 2935 cm^{-1} that represents aliphatic C-H bonds. Another relevant peak is observed at 1654 cm^{-1} , which represents aromatic C=N groups. Vibrations with a band at 1190 cm^{-1} indicate the C-N stretching of the OCT. Aside from the aliphatic C-H bonds present in OCT, samples with coated OCT have an almost identical spectrum to the original hydrogel film, OCT peak at 1654 cm^{-1} is in hydrogel film slightly shifted to the lower wavelengths at 1607 cm^{-1} proving presence of OCT. Low absorbance of OCT absorbance in sample might be caused by its low concentration and the fact that OCT is present primarily in the dense hydrogel surface layer, and FTIR detects the bulk instead of the upper hydrogel layers. Moreover, the presentation of the OCT on the hydrogel surface was confirmed also by EDS analysis as described later (see Table 3). Overall, the characteristic bands represented by all components were confirmed in the hydrogel matrix; however, various ratios between components clearly show, in normalised curves, that the corresponding signal to each component relies on its concentration in the dry hydrogel, although ATR-FTIR is not a primarily quantitative method.

3.5. Thermal Stability of Hydrogel Films

The thermal stability of the hydrogel films was instrumentally measured using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) under a nitrogen atmosphere. **Figure 5A** shows the thermal degradation of the chemicals, which can be compared with the degradation steps of the prepared hydrogel films in Error! Reference source not found.s **5B and C** and the coated hydrogel films in **Figure 5D**. The first mass loss occurred at temperatures below 200 °C, attributed to bounded water. For Series 1 (25 wt% of glycerol) (**Figure 5B**), the hydrogels exhibit two-step degradation with similar curve shapes for samples (1GPgL, 2GPgL, and 3GPgL) in the 90 - 350 °C range. The first peak can contribute to the decomposition of glycerol and water residues; the second peak represents the decomposition of PVA and GK with solid residues at 700 °C with 26.38, 23.07, and 29.77 wt% of stable GK residues. The mass loss in Series 2 (75 wt% of glycerol) (**Figure 5C**) degrades mainly in the range of 110 – 205 °C, indicating the decomposition step of glycerol due to its high concentration and bounded water. The second stage of decomposition is for PVA and GK in the range of 270 to 370 °C, with the remaining solid residues of GK and PVA 10.17 (1GPgH), 11.74 (2GPgH) and 13.51 wt% (3GPgH). The cross-linked network between PVA, GK, and glycerol did not significantly impact the thermal

stability of the hydrogel film; only the mass concentration and the glycerol layer on the surface could affect the thermal stability. The percentage of mass corresponds to the weight ratio of each component in the hydrogel. Overall, the thermal degradation of all tested samples is directly proportional to the hydrogel composition, so physical cross-linking via hydrogen bonding, PVA crystalline domains and polymer chain entanglement do not significantly influence this kind of degradation and overall thermal stability. Both coated hydrogel films in **Figure 5D** have the same initial weight loss as the original hydrogel films due to the presented bounded water. The second and third decomposition steps have parallel curves with uncoated films, showing that OCT has no significant impact on the hydrogel thermal stability due to its low concentration. The only difference between noncoated and coated films is the larger mass of residues after the measurement, which the presence of OCT might cause. However, there were no additional TGA measurements of OCT because of minimum differences. From the

Figure 5: TGA curves and derived weight curves of raw materials (A), hydrogel films with different compositions (B), GK hydrogels (C), and OCT coated hydrogel films (D). *m* in graph represents mass loss.

results, we can conclude that OCT coating had no impact on hydrogel composition and cross-linking and did not affect the thermal decomposition of the hydrogel film.

3.6. Mechanical Properties of Hydrogel Films

The tensile strength behaviour of the hydrogel films was evaluated in the hydrated state to determine the stretchability and endurance of the samples while handling them. The test was carried out at 37 °C in ultrapure water; the hydrogel was placed in two grips and hydrated until equilibrium; sample 3GPgL was not used due to its brittle state in the dry state. The curves of the hydrated films are shown in **Figure 6**. Each curve represents the average behaviour of the samples; even though the hydrogels have different values for the breaking point, the shape of the curves is similar.

Figure 6: Average tensile curves for various sample compositions in water at 37 °C after equilibrium swelling degree of hydrogels.

Figures 7A and B show a statistical comparison of the hydrogel break point; from the results, the applied stress of each sample is incomparable due to differences in composition and physical properties. The highest stiffness of the material against applied stress exhibited the sample 2GPgH (75 wt% of glycerol), with a high-density polymer network consisting mainly of PVA and glycerol with a breakpoint of 128.7 ± 11.37 kPa. The remaining samples had applied stress values approximately four times lower, around 31.7 ± 2.1 kPa. The material's stiffness decreases with increasing GK concentration since it has no significant mechanical properties

and increases dissolution (1GPgL, 3GPgH)¹⁸. The viscoelastic behaviour of the films contributed to the glycerol content, which increases elongation (139.1 ± 7.0 % for 1GPgH, 148.15 ± 10.9 % for 2GPgH and $104.1 \pm 7.7\%$ for 3GPgH compared to the original length) compared to the brittle Series 1 with a low glycerol concentration (**Figure 7B**).

Figure 7: Comparison of applied stress on the hydrogel films at a breakpoint (A), an average elongation of the hydrogel films at the breakpoint (B).

3.7. Hydrogel Films Morphology and Porous Structure

The self-improved A-ESEM microscope equipped with an ionisation secondary electron detector with an electrostatic separator (ISEDS)⁵⁰ was used to evaluate the hydrogel film morphology. Prior to the A-ESEM observation, all samples were prepared via freeze-drying of polymer blend solutions in various polymer ratios; the first freeze-drying process achieved the porous structure. In the beginning, the surface morphology of the hydrogel was visualised in the dry state (**Figure 8**). The hydrogel was then hydrated and *in situ* freeze-dried^{51,43} in a specimen chamber of the microscope. This very fast processing allowed the stabilisation of the inner porous structure to close to the natural state as if applied as transparent coating⁵² (**Figure 9**). Furthermore, the sample was cracked after snapping in liquid nitrogen to characterise the antiseptic layer and changes caused by the coating (**Figure 11**). The surfaces of non-hydrated samples are shown in **Figure 8**; A) sample 1GPgL (1:1 GK:PVA ratio, 25 wt% glycerol) shows a porous network, while B) sample 2GPgL (1:2 GK:PVA ratio, 25 wt% glycerol) tends to have a much smoother surface with a porous network that is not precisely defined due to the presence of a dense, smooth layer coating the surface. Samples 1GPgH and 2GPgH (75 wt% glycerol), as seen in **Figure 8C-D**, have a porous structure that is not precisely defined on the surface; the

glycerol-polymer layer coats the surface. Based on the A-ESEM images, the porous structure is located beneath the surface layer of 1GPgH and 2GPgH hydrogels and is composed mainly of glycerol and PVA. The presence of glycerol significantly influences the anti-freezing properties of the material as it prevents water from freezing⁵³. It can explain the absence of pores in the surface layer where glycerol is present, together with the fact that the hydrogel film surface layer is frozen faster than the hydrogel film in bulk, so there is no time and space for ice crystals to grow, forming a porogen for subsequent drying⁵⁴. The fabrication method of freeze drying of the original polymer blend can influence the formation of compact and smooth hydrogel film surfaces, as described in Sornkamnerd et al.⁵⁵ and Simoni et al.⁵⁶. The appearance

Figure 8: A-ESEM surface images of GK-based hydrogels after freeze-drying; A) 1GPgL, B) 2GPgL, C) 1GPgH, D) 2GPgH.

of these pores differs compared to untreated samples (**Figure 8A-B**), which after hydration and subsequent *in situ* freeze-drying tend to have more round and smoother pore walls **Figure 9A-B**. The surface and bulk morphology of the Series 2 samples (75 wt% glycerol – 1GPgH and 2GPgH) are visualised after *in situ* freeze-drying using A-ESEM. This method is essential since the hydrogel surface layer of Series 2 samples is susceptible to radiation damage and tends to degrade rapidly using conventional scanning electron microscopy as described by Samadi et

al.⁵⁷. Samples with a 25% weight percent of glycerol from Series 1 images (**Figure 9A-B**) of the *in-situ* freeze-dried hydrogels showed a microporous network with an average pore size of $7.8 \pm 5.1 \mu\text{m}$ for 1GPgL and $15.6 \pm 13.6 \mu\text{m}$ for 2GPgL (**Figure 10**). The average pore size of Series 2 ($3 \mu\text{m}$ for sample 1GPgH and $3.8 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$ for 2GPgH, representing a slight decrease in pore size; this trend could be caused by a higher concentration of glycerol and the formation of the surface layer in samples 1GPgH and 2GPgH).

Figure 9: A-ESEM images after in situ the freeze-dried hydrogels of 1GPgL (A), 2GPgL (B), 1GPgH porous network (C), 1GPgH hydrogel surface (D), 2GPgH porous network (E), hydrogel surface of 2GPgH (F).

Figure 10: In situ freeze-dried hydrogel pore size from A-ESEM image estimated by SEMIPE.

The visual aspect of the surface layer before (**Figure 8C-D**) and after (**Figure 9D, F**) *in-situ* freeze-drying is diverse, indicating that the second freeze-drying influences the visual aspect of the hydrogel surface. The chemical composition of the hydrogel and the ratio between the components strongly determine the visual aspect of the hydrogel and the porosity, which affects the physical behaviour of the final hydrogel. A higher concentration of the polymers (GK and PVA) can form a network with a larger pore size. The opposite trend occurs when a plasticizer (glycerol) is added, creating a dense outer hydrogel layer with a porous network beneath the surface and a decrease in pore size. The chemical composition of the hydrogel and the ratio between the components strongly determine the visual aspect of the hydrogel and the porosity, which affects the physical behaviour of the final hydrogel. A higher concentration of the polymers (GK and PVA) can form a network with a larger pore size. The opposite trend occurs when glycerol is added, creating a dense outer hydrogel layer with a porous network beneath the surface and decreased pore size. Subsequently, the 1GPgH and 2GPgH samples were coated with antiseptic OCT. A-ESEM visualised the morphology differences caused by the OCT coating on the hydrogel surface and the lateral cuts. The non-hydrated hydrogels 1GPgH (**Figure 11C**) and 2GPgH (**Figure 11D**) show no visible antiseptic structures or dried antiseptic crystals. Furthermore, the lateral cuts of the hydrogels do not show additional visible antiseptic layers or crystals on the hydrogel surface (**Figure 11A and B**). Based on these outcomes, we can conclude that the antiseptics were likely absorbed by the dense surface layer and possibly

penetrated to the hydrogel bulk. This absorption might be due to the film coating with OCT when the antiseptic is dissolved in ethanol, which slightly disrupts the glycerol surface layer and then rapidly evaporates, forming a porous and smooth hydrogel surface.

Figure 11: Lateral cuts through the non-hydrated samples 1GPgH-oH (A), 2GPgH-oH (B), in situ freeze-dried, and hydrogel surface of C) 1GPgH-oH (C) and 2GPgH-oH (D).

Because there is no visible antiseptic layer on the surface, EDS analysis was performed on the coated hydrogels to verify and determine the presence of OCT on the hydrogel film surface or in the matrix, focussing on the analysis of chlorine (Cl) and nitrogen (N) elements. **Table 3** shows the cross-sectional elemental analysis of samples 1GPgH and 2GPgH with and without OCT coating. Although the results of semiquantitative EDS analysis are only approximate, OCT is present in a very low concentration; chlorine was detected in both samples at the detection limit. Sample 1GPgH-oH contains only a small amount of the element, accounting for 1.29%, and the chlorine concentration in sample 2GPgH-oH accounts for approximately 0.1%. This low concentration could be because EDS detects the OCT layer, and the deeper layer of chlorine penetrates the matrix. Since there is a dense layer based on glycerol on the hydrogel surface of the 2GPgH sample, the penetration of OCT is limited, and these elements may not be detected. The elevated concentration of elemental nitrogen shows a much higher

presence of OCT in the sample 1GPgH-oH, with an increase of 0.2% compared to the original hydrogel. The hydrogel morphology strongly determines the penetration of OCT into the hydrogel surface layer and the matrix, and the low concentration limits the analysis. Despite this, the concentration of OCT presented is sufficient for antibacterial activity, as mentioned in Chapter 3.9. UV-VIS confirmed the exact coated OCT concentration via a release study in Chapter 3.6.

Table 3: Analysis of the content of elements on the hydrogel surface by EDS.

sample	N (%)	Cl (%)
1GPgH	0.8	0.0
1GPgH-oL	1.0	0.1
1GPgH-oH	1.1	1.3
2GPgH	1.1	0.0
2GPgH-oL	0.8	0.1
2GPgH-oH	1.0	0.1

3.8. Release Kinetics of Octenidine Dihydrochloride

A cumulative *in vitro* release study determined the release of OCT from GK-based hydrogels. Given the nature of the sample and the fact that OCT is coated on the hydrogel surface, an initial rapid release of the drug was expected. The presence of OCT on the hydrogel surface was confirmed using EDS analysis in Chapter 3.7 despite the analysis reaching its low limit. **Figure 12** shows a rapid OCT release followed by a sustained release over two weeks. The release kinetics are influenced by the coating method, hydrogel composition, and hydrogel film behaviour in an aqueous environment as hydrogel easily binds water, indicating that OCT release might also be dependent on swelling behaviour and its subsequent hydrolytic stability as described in chapters 3.2 and 3.3. **Figure 12** shows that all release profiles have similar curves with the expected initial significant burst release of OCT, as described by Moritz et al.³³. Curve profiles indicate that the release mechanism is consistent across all tested samples. To understand OCT release kinetics from the hydrogel, release curves were fitted with Higuchi and KP mathematical release kinetics models. The KP model fitted the best for all tested samples

with the correlation coefficient R^2 values over 0.97 – 0.99 and n exponent ≤ 0.46 , indicating that Fickian diffusion contributes to OCT release from the hydrogel surface.

Figure 12: Cumulative release of OCT from the hydrogel film surface.

Diffusion is driven by the concentration gradient between OCT in the hydrogel's surface layer and the solvent. The concentration gradient is highest at the beginning of the experiment, correlating with the measurement results. 24% of OCT was released from sample 1GPgH-oH (having a higher concentration of $0.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) within the first hour, while 34% was released from sample 1GPgH-oL ($0.05 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$). Conversely, 2GPgH samples showed a faster release, approximately 42 – 43 % in both samples (2GPgH-oL/H), indicating that OCT binding to the hydrogel surface and matrix beneath depends on the composition. This uncoated sample (2GPgH) also showed the highest stiffness and elongation, indicating a strong cross-linked network and thus releasing the highest amount of OCT that was probably weaker bounded to the hydrogel film surface than in the case of 1GPgH-oL or 1GPgH-oH. After the initial burst, all hydrogel film release profiles became more gradual but continuous even after 14 days, confirming the diffusion mechanism driven by decreasing OCT concentration over time. Only the 2GPgH-oL sample released all weakly-coated OCT during the experiment. Generally, samples with a lower OCT concentration released approximately 10-20 % higher amounts of OCT than those with a higher concentration, suggesting that OCT concentration influences binding to the hydrogel. A lower dose might not disrupt the hydrogel surface layer, allowing easier diffusion when in contact with a solvent. As shown in **Figure 12**, OCT was present in

samples 1GPgH-oL/H and 2GPgH-oH at the end of the experiment (after 14 days). This indicates that OCT is both coated on the surface and also loaded deeper into the hydrogel matrix.

The dense surface layer and OCT's ability to load deeper under the surface layer into the hydrogel matrix might cause OCT entrapment, making OCT release slower.

3.8.1. Cytotoxicity of OCT-Coated Hydrogel Films

The extract method was used to assess the cytotoxic effect of hydrogel films on NIH-3T3 fibroblasts. This method was adopted for the in vitro cytotoxicity evaluation of materials that may release leachable toxic components from the material or the exposed surface. The extraction conditions (time \approx 24 hrs and temperature \approx 37 °C) were chosen according to the physicochemical characteristics of the hydrogels, such as degradation and OCT release (**Figures 3 and 12**). **A** shows the viability of NIH-3T3 cells exposed to extracts of GPgL series with 25 wt% glycerol and GPgH series with 75 wt% glycerol. The extracts of the OCT-free sample did not induce any significant cytotoxic effect on cells compared to the plastic control. In fact, viability decreased the most (79%; $p \leq 0.01$) for 2GPgH hydrogel. This could be attributed to the high glycerol release from the sample, according to the higher percentage of hydrogel degradation (32% after 24 hrs). Considering PVA as a biocompatible material, glycerol at higher concentrations has also shown cytotoxic effects, as reported elsewhere^{58,59}. The viability assay of the selected antiseptic extracts of the OCT sample is shown in **Figure 13B**. The assay revealed a dependence on cytotoxicity on OCT concentration in NIH-3T3 fibroblasts, which is correlated with the OCT release test (**Figure 12**). In our results, the viability of the 1GPgh-oL sample is 60%, and the viability of the 1GPgh-oH, 2GPgh-oL and 2GPgh-oH samples reached less than 50%. These results correspond to the decreased viability cells in the presence of OCT in samples in a dose-dependent manner, as reported elsewhere^{60,61}.

Figure 13: Cytotoxicity studies of OCT-free hydrogel extracts (A) and OCT-coated hydrogel films extracts (B), the antibacterial activity of OCT-coated GK-based hydrogel films against Gram-positive and Gram-negative resistant bacterial strains: *Staphylococcus aureus* (C) and *Escherichia coli* (D).

3.9. Antibacterial Activity of OCT-Coated Hydrogel Films

Antibacterial activity against multidrug-resistant bacterial strains is an essential property nowadays since it is a worldwide problem requiring innovative solutions for effectively suppressing and eliminating bacterial infections. Therefore, the GK-based hydrogel film 1GPpH and 2GPpH with and without coated OCT were tested for antibacterial activity using the broth microdilution methodology. The antimicrobial effect was determined based on the growth curves obtained from individual bacterial strains. *S. aureus* and *E. coli* were chosen to represent Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains. From the results shown in **Figures 13C and D**, we can conclude that materials without coated OCT (1GPpH, 2GPpH) do

not significantly inhibit the growth of bacterial strains. The GK in the hydrogel matrix shows limited antibacterial properties since it has a low concentration. Anyhow, sample 1GPgH, having a higher amount of GK, exhibited much higher bacterial inhibition than 2GPgH, where PVA prevails. Drápalová et al.⁴⁸ and Lipový et al.⁶² proved GK's antibacterial activity on different bacterial strains. On the other hand, hydrogel films coated with OCT showed complete inhibition of bacterial growth in both tested materials and concentrations, indicating sufficient OCT elution from the hydrogel with the desired antimicrobial effect. Therefore, we can conclude that even low OCT concentrations (0.05 and 0.1%) exhibit high antibacterial efficacy compared to the literature^{63,64}.

Conclusions

This study successfully developed and characterised innovative freeze-dried hydrogel films based on GK and PVA with antibacterial OCT, showcasing their potential for various applications beyond wound healing. The films demonstrated unique physicochemical properties, influenced by the specific composition and fabrication method, which shaped their distinctive morphology and overall performance. Enhanced transparency, mechanical stability, non-toxicity and antibacterial efficacy were achieved by carefully manipulating GK, glycerol and PVA content coated with OCT. Hydrogels with higher glycerol concentrations exhibited smaller pore sizes, leading to increased light transmission, thus improving transparency and enhanced elasticity with mechanical stability, making them suitable for transparent coatings and biomedical devices. The hydrogels maintained long-term stability in wet environments, as shown by swelling and degradation studies, particularly those with higher PVA and glycerol content. Adding low doses of OCT significantly improved antibacterial activity against Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria, with sustained release over several days, effectively suppressing infections. Biocompatibility assessments indicated that while GK/PVA hydrogels were not cytotoxic, incorporating OCT increased cytotoxicity, suggesting that optimizing OCT concentration could enhance cell viability while preserving antibacterial efficacy. These insights into the composition-structure relationship highlight the versatility of GK-based hydrogels as multifunctional materials, with potential applications extending from wound healing and infection control to other uses requiring transparent, mechanically stable, and antibacterial surfaces. According to the aforementioned requirements, the best composition fulfilling all goals seems to be sandwich-like sample 1GPgH-oL involving 1:1 GK:PVA, 75% glycerol and only 0.05% coated octenidine dihydrochloride. The sample is transparent in both

dry and hydrated states, showing great porosity, elasticity and good stiffness, great stability, non-cytotoxicity and excellent antibacterial efficacy. Future research will explore further enrichment with alternative antimicrobial agents, broadening the scope of applications for these innovative biomaterial hydrogel films. Their adaptability makes them suitable for drug delivery systems, tissue scaffolds, flexible bioelectronics, and environmental remediation, demonstrating their broad impact on various fields.

Author's contributions

All authors participated in discussing the results and writing and revising the manuscript. E. Černá: management of the experiments, fabrication, and characterisation (swelling behaviour, hydrogel degradation, optical properties, tensile strength test, drug release, TGA, FTIR) manuscript writing, E. Tihlaříková, and V. Neděla: characterisation (morphology, EDS analysis), manuscript revision, J. Matulová: characterisation (TGA), L. Vacek: characterisation (antibacterial test), Z. Fohlerová characterisation, and manuscript writing (cytotoxicity assay), J. Brtníková, L. Vojtová, and B. Lipový: writing – review & editing, propose the concept and experiments, funding acquisition, and supervision.

Data availability

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found online as Dataset in Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15738067>.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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